

A STUDY ON IMPACT OF WORK STRESS ON INDIVIDUAL LIFE OF BANK EMPLOYEES AT SELECTED BRANCHES IN MEERUT CITY

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ABSTRACT

It has been noted in various news & studies that a majority of the employees face severe stress related ailments and many psychological problems in the organizations. Hence, the management must take necessary initiatives in helping their employees to overcome the disastrous effects of work stress, because employees spend roughly one third of their lives working in an organization. Employees, who are stressed, are also more likely to be unhealthy, poorly motivated, less productive and less safe at work. This way, work stress can be a real problem to the organization as well as for its workers. Therefore, this study can be helpful in assessing the level of stress experienced by the bank employees, in identifying major causes and effect of work stress on such employees and in exploring various methods to manage stress. It will also try to provide the necessary suggestions and findings for the bank employees to manage such burden of stress in order to improve their performance and increase their productivity. Therefore, an attempt is made to analyze the impact of work stress on individual life of bank employees. The present study is based on survey method using both primary and secondary data. Primary data have been collected directly from 10 leading public and private banks at Meerut city of Western Uttar Pradesh using simple random method. 10 employees have been taken as sample from each bank branch. The total employees covered have been 100.

INTRODUCTION

Today, work stress is becoming a major issue and a matter of concern for the employees and the organizations as well. Challenging job assignment followed by moderate doses of competitive spirit, constructive conflict and zeal to get ahead of others have increased the stress at work. Hans Selye first introduced the concept of stress in 1936. He defined stress as "The force, pressure, or strain exerted upon a material object or person which resist these forces and attempt to maintain its original state."

Steers indicates that, "Occupational stress has become an important topic for study of organizational behaviour for several reasons - 1. Stress has harmful psychological and physiological effects on employees, 2. Stress is a major cause of employee turnover and absenteeism, 3. Stress experienced by one employee can affect the safety of other employees, 4. By controlling dysfunctional stress, individual and organization can be managed more effectively."

According to National Institute of Health, "stress can reduce the enjoyment in life, cause hypertension, cardiac problems, reduce immunity, contribute to substance abuse, lead to frustration, irritability and reduce the overall status of mental and physical well-being."

Work stress affects the work performance, memory, concentration, and learning. Stress at work also provides a serious risk of litigation for all employers and organizations, carrying significant liabilities for damages, bad publicity and loss of reputation. Dealing with stress-related claims also consumes vast amounts of management time. Employers should provide a stress-free work environment, recognize where stress is becoming a problem for staff, and take action to reduce stress. Stress in the workplace reduces productivity, increases management pressures, and makes people ill in many ways, evidence of which is still increasing. Therefore, there are clearly strong economic and financial reasons for organisations to manage and reduce stress at work, aside from the obvious humanitarian and ethical considerations. The growth of industries, pressure in the urban areas, quantitative growth in population, various problems in day-to-day life and the general complexities of social environment are some of the reasons for increase in stress. Stress is an unavoidable consequence of modern living. Stress is a condition of strain that has a direct bearing on emotions, thought-process and physical conditions of a person.

The banking sector had undergone rapid transformations owing to policy reforms, increased competition, and downsizing, introduction of new technologies, and recently the demonetization & cashless transactions. These changes have put a high level of stress on the bank employees. Thus, the advent of these policy level and technological changes has modified the work patterns of the bank employees and affected the social, economic and psychological domains of the bank employees and their relations. In addition, these factors are the prospective attributes to cause the work stress and related disorders among the Bank Employees.

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NEED OF STUDY

It has been noted in various news & studies that a majority of the employees face severe stress related ailments and many psychological problems in the organizations. Hence, the management must take necessary initiatives in helping their employees to overcome the disastrous effects of work stress, because employees spend roughly one third of their lives working in an organization. Employees, who are stressed, are also more likely to be unhealthy, poorly motivated, less productive and less safe at work. This way, work stress can be a real problem to the organization as well as for its workers. Therefore, this study can be helpful in assessing the level of stress experienced by the bank employees, in identifying major causes and effect of work stress on such employees and in exploring various methods to manage stress. It will also try to provide the necessary suggestions and findings for the bank employees to manage such burden of stress in order to improve their performance and increase their productivity. Therefore, keeping all this in mind and the discussions made above, an attempt is made to analyze the impact of work stress on individual life of bank employees at 10 selected banks-branches in Meerut City of Western Uttar Pradesh.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Behr and Newman (1978) define occupational stress as "A condition arising from the interaction of people and their jobs and characterized by changes within people that force them to deviate from their normal functioning."

Cobb (1975) has the opinion that, "The responsibility load creates severe stress among workers and managers." If the individual manager cannot cope with the increased responsibilities, it may lead to several physical and psychological disorders among them.

Brook (1973) reported that qualitative changes in the job create adjust mental problem among employees. The interpersonal relationships within the department and between the departments create qualitative difficulties within the organisation largely.

Miles and Perrault (1976) identify four different types of role conflict: a) Intra-sender role conflict, b) Inter sender role conflict, c) Person- role conflict, and d) Role over load.

Ivancevich and Matteson (1950) indicate, "Lack of group cohesiveness may explain various physiological and behavioural outcomes in an employ desiring such sticks together."

Lack of participation in the decision making process, lack of effective consultation and communication, unjustified restrictions on behaviour, office politics and no sense of belonging are identified as potential sources of stressors. Lack of participation in work activity is associated with negative psychological mood and behavioural responses, including escapist drinking and heavy smoking (Capelin et al., 1975).

French and Caplan (1975), "Pressure of both qualitative and quantitative overload can result in the need to work excessive hours, which is an additional source of stress." Having to work under time pressure in order to meet deadlines is an independent source of stress. Studies show that stress levels increase as difficult deadlines draw near.

Occupational stress is an increasingly important occupational health problem and a significant cause of economic loss. Occupational stress may produce both overt psychological and physiological disabilities. However, it may also cause subtle manifestation of morbidity that can affect personal well-being and productivity (Quick, Murphy, Harrell and Orman, 1992).

SCOPE OF STUDY

This study has been done in Meerut city of Western Uttar Pradesh. The metropolitan city of Meerut is an industrial hub as much as agricultural and allied activity. Meerut is 70 kilometers North West from New Delhi and about 453 kilometers from Lucknow, the state capital of Uttar Pradesh. The strategic location of this region on the fertile plains of Rivers Ganga and Hindon, a tributary of Yamuna, is conducive for agriculture and allied activities. The state is spread across 2590 square kilometers and is situated at 77 degrees and 78 degrees longitude East and 28° 54' and 29° 15' latitude North, Meerut city is divided into Mawana, Sardhana and Meerut Divisions. The whole region of Meerut enjoys physical and climatic conditions, coupled with adequate rainfall-the reasons that have fostered agricultural development here. As a Prominent contribution of New Delhi, the city became part of the National Capital Region (NCR) that has fostered the development of this region.

Meerut is situated on the vast plains that are bounded by River Ganges on the east and River Hindon on the west. The average rainfall here is about 586 mm, monsoons begin by the end of June, and lasts till the end of September. The alluvial soil grains deposited from both the rivers is what makes this whole region most suitable for agriculture.

Due to rapid industrialization and development in the city, there has been a demographic shift of people from nearby villages and towns to Meerut city. As per the 2011 census, the population of Meerut stood at 3.4 million. Out of the total 3447405 people 1829192 was the male population and the rest 1618213 was female population. As per the previous recorded population in 2001, there has been a rise of 15.92% in a span of 10 years. Meerut ranks the 26th most populated city in India. Owing to the high developmental activities in this region, the population density of Meerut is relatively very high. The population density of Meerut is 1347 people/square km. This is the sixth highest in the country and second highest in the NCR Region.

The literacy of Meerut Population is 74.80%, as per the 2011 census, while the state average is 69.72%. 2001 census stated that the male literacy ratio was 76.31%, and that of female literacy was 54.21%.

The city has branches of nearly all public and private banks except foreign banks. 10 leading banks Branches have taken for the study. No comparison between public and private banks- employees has been made here. This study is focused only on employees working as cashier, teller and routine clerks in the banks whether public or private. Any other employees have not been included in this study.

METHODOLOGY AND OBJECTIVES OF STUDY

The following are the main objectives of the present study:

- To identify the workload, work procedures and working hours related stress among bank employees at selected bank branches in Meerut city.
- To examine the impact of workload, work procedures and working hours related stress on individual life of bank employees in Meerut city.

The present study is based on survey method using both primary and secondary data. Primary data have been collected directly from 10 leading public and private banks at Meerut city using simple random method. 10 employees have been taken as sample from each bank branch. The total employees covered have been 100. Interview and questionnaire methods have been used as instrument to collect primary data. Questionnaire consisting of 31 questions was distributed in 3 sets to 100 bank employees and 100% response was got from them in filling the questions. Secondary data for the study have been collected from books, journals, internet and the like.

DEMOGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS OF RESPONDENTS

The demographic characteristics is important to analyze in the stress related studies such as marital status, years of experience, educational qualification are directly connected with the impact of stress and coping style of stress. Social, personal, self-esteem and appearance are some important fields. The lack in these statuses may cause stress. Table-1 explains the Demographic characteristics of the sample respondents.

Table-1: Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents

S. No.	Factor / Category	Number of Respondents	Percentage (%)
1.	Gender		
	Male	40	40
	Female	60	60
	Total	100	100
2.	Marital Status		
	Married	90	90
	Unmarried	10	10
	Total	100	100
3.	Age		
	Below 20 years	15	15
	Between 20-25 years	33	33
	Between 25-30 years	26	26
	Above 30 years	26	26

	Total	100	100
4.	Educational Qualification		
	Graduate	82	82
	Post Graduate and More	18	18
	Total	100	100
5.	Working Experience		
	Below 1 year	17	17
	Between 1 and 3 years	44	44
	Between 3 and 5 years	26	26
	Above 5 years	13	13
	Total	100	100
6.	Income		
	Satisfied	65	65
	Dissatisfied	16	16
	Ok	19	19
	Total	100	100

Sources: Primary Data

It is understood from table-1 that shows that majority of the bank employees are females (60%) and married (90%). Most of the bank employees are in the age group between 20 and 25 years (33%) and 18% bank employees are post graduate or more qualified. Majority of the bank employees are between the working experiences of 1 to 3 years and more number of bank employees have satisfied income.

Work Load Related Stress

Workload is chief culprit in creating stress among bank employees. It may be in the form of looking after too many customers in the branch, having more responsibility, carrying out others work, and doing non-professional work, lack of man power in the branch develop stress and affect their individual life. The workload stress is depicted in the Table-2.

Table-2: Work Load

S. No.	Statement	SA (5)	A (4)	NO (3)	DA (2)	SDA (1)	Weighted Score	Rank
1.	I have too many customers at my seat.	72	26	0	1	1	4.67	2
2.	I am assigned too much responsibility.	35	40	0	13	12	3.53	10
3.	I have too much work.	86	9	0	4	3	4.77	1
4.	I am often under pressure to work overtime.	60	33	0	4	3	4.49	4
5.	I am also responsible for computers documentation and other things at my seat.	42	24	4	15	15	3.63	9
6.	I have too many different things to do.	44	35	4	14	3	4.03	5
7.	I am doing some administration work also (e.g. supervisory work).	40	30	2	18	10	3.72	7
8.	There is inadequate staff in my branch.	43	25	3	15	14	3.68	8
9.	I have constant time pressure due to heavy workload.	73	23	0	3	1	4.64	3
10.	I perform nonprofessional tasks such as delivering and retrieving documents, stationary disbursement and ordering, co-ordering or performing ancillary services.	45	25	0	20	10	3.95	6

Sources: Primary Data

It is understood from the table-2 that, having too much work, having too many customers at my seat constant time pressure due to heavy work load, being under pressure to work overtime are the foremost work load related stress producing work stress among bank employees as they have scored the rank of 1st, 2nd, 3rd and 4th. Having too many different things to do and performing nonprofessional tasks are the next foremost work load related stress causing stress among bank employees and they have scored the 5th and 6th rank respectively. Doing some administration work also inadequate staff in the branch, being responsible for computers and documents and other things, assigning too many responsibility are the workload related stress producing stress among bank employees and they have scored 8th, 8th, 9th, and 10th rank respectively.

Impact of Work Load, Work Procedures and Working Hours Related Stress on Individual Life of Bank Employees

Stress may differ to different persons. It may take different forms such as anger, depression, and lack of involvement in the work, aggressive behaviour and receiving complaints from colleagues and customers. It will not only be fatal to the health of the bank employees but also works negatively on the treatment of the customers. Table 4 depicts the impact of workload, work procedures and working hours related stress on individual life on bank employees.

Table-3: Impact on Individual Life

S. No.	Statement	SA (5)	A (4)	NO (3)	DA (2)	SDA (1)	Weighted Score	Rank
1.	My morale and self-esteem is affected.	68	28	2	1	1	4.61	2
2.	I have the feeling of nervousness, anger, aggression, fear, anxiety.	29	31	2	20	18	3.39	15
3.	My concentration, attention, decision is affected.	64	36	0	0	0	4.64	1
4.	I fall sick frequently.	60	35	0	3	2	4.48	4
5.	I feel depressed and uninvolved in the work.	40	28	2	14	16	3.62	12
6.	I am not able to balance my work and home life.	31	32	2	18	17	3.42	14
7.	I am not able to finish the work in time.	40	30	2	18	10	3.72	9
8.	I express over reaction to small things.	35	40	0	13	12	3.53	13
9.	I receive complaint from the coworkers.	65	29	0	4	2	4.51	3
10.	I receive complaints from the customers.	45	25	0	20	10	3.95	8
11.	I find difficulty to recall the officer instruction and understanding routine procedures.	50	40	0	4	6	4.24	7
12.	I take longer time to complete deadlines and daily job function.	42	24	4	15	15	3.63	11
13.	I find on the job absenteeism (Being physically at work but have difficulty in concentrating on job).	52	39	0	3	6	4.28	6
14.	I find difficulty in thinking logically and making decisions.	51	41	0	5	3	4.32	5
15.	I encounter difficulty for relaxation.	43	25	3	15	14	3.68	10

Sources: Primary Data

It is clearly known from the Table 4 that affection of concentration, attention and decision, affection of morale and self-esteem, receiving complaints from the co-workers, falling in sick frequently and finding difficulty in thinking logically and making decisions are the foremost impact of work stress on individual life of bank employees and they have scored the rank of 1st, 2nd, 3rd, 4th and 5th rank respectively. Finding on the job absenteeism (Being physically at work but have difficulty in concentrating on the job), finding difficulty to recall the officers instruction and understanding routine procedures, receiving complaints from the customers, inability to finish the work in time and encountering difficulty for relaxation are the next foremost effect of work stress on individual life of bank employees and they have scored the 5th, 6th, 7th, 8th, 9th and 10th rank respectively. Taking longer time to complete deadlines and daily job function, feeling depressed and uninvolved in the work, expressing over reaction to small things, inability to balance work and home life and having the feeling of nervousness, anger aggression, fear, anxiety are the least effect of work stress on individual life of bank employees and they have scored 11th, 12th and 13th and 14th and 15th rank respectively.

FINDINGS OF STUDY

The following are the findings of this study.

Majority of the bank employees are females (60%) and married (90%). Most of the bank employees are in the age group between 20 and 25 years (33%) and some of the bank employees are qualified with Post Graduate Degree or More (18%). Majority of the bank employees are between the working experiences of 1 to 3 years and maximum bank employees are satisfied with income.

Having too much work, having too many customers on their seat, constant time pressure due to heavy work load, being under pressure to work overtime are the foremost work load related stress producing work stress among bank employees as they have scored the rank of 1st, 2nd, 3rd and 4th rank. Having too many different things to do and doing administration work during officer is not available in the branch are the next foremost work load related stress causing stress among bank employee and they have scored the 5th and 6th rank respectively. Doing some administration work also (e.g. clerical work), Inadequate staff in the branch, being responsible for computers, documentations and other things, assigning too many responsibility are the work load related stress producing stress among bank employees and they have scored 7th, 8th and 10th rank respectively.

Affection of concentration, attention and decision, affection of morale and self-esteem, receiving complaints from the customers, falling sick frequently and finding difficulty in thinking logically and making decisions are the foremost impact of work stress on individual life of bank employees and they have scored the rank of 1st, 2nd, 3rd, 4th and 5th rank respectively. Finding on the job absenteeism (Being physically at work but have difficulty in concentrating on the job), Finding difficulty to recall the officer's instruction and understanding routine procedures, receiving complaints from the customers, inability to finish the work in time and encountering difficulty for relaxation are the next foremost effect of work stress on individual life of bank employees and they scored 5th, 6th, 7th, 8th, 9th and 10th rank respectively. Taking longer time to complete deadlines and daily job function, feeling depressed and uninvolved in the work, expressing over reaction to small things, inability to balance work and home life and having the feeling of nervousness, anger, aggression, fear, anxiety are the least effect of work stress on individual life of bank employees and they have scored 11th, 12th and 13th, 14th and 15th rank respectively.

Workload, work procedures and working hours related stress has a negative impact on individual life of bank employees.

SUGGESTIONS

Based on the study the following suggestions may be put forth:

Sufficient number of staff may be appointed to reduce the workload of the bank employees. Some kind of relaxation techniques, which can be done at work and suitable for reducing depression, anxiety, aggression, fear, may be taught.

Working hours may be defined appropriately. Equality in the allocation of work may be followed to improve the morale and motivation to the bank employees.

In order to improve the concentration, attention and decision they may be relieved from performing non-professional tasks such as delivering and retrieving documents, stationary disbursement and ordering, coordinating, or performing ancillary services. The supportive services should properly be trained to reduce the workload of the bank employees.

Separate in-charge may be appointed for computers and documents in the branch in order to make the bank employees work peacefully. Allotment of the customers in the branch should be followed according to the number of bank employees in the branch since most of the respondents have said that their workload is increased by looking after more customers in the branch and being responsible for computers and documentations in the branch. Bank employees may be allowed in the decision making process with regard to their branch. The communication channel with the officers and supervisors may be developed to improve the involvement and motivation of the bank employees. The frequent meeting can be conducted in the manner that all departmental staff can be joined together to improve the better relationship among different departmental staffs and minimized the conflict among them. In the place where more number of female bank employees is working, the sufficient number of rest room, drinking water facilities may be made.

CONCLUSION

It is hence, proved that work load, work procedures and working hours related stress have a negative bearing to the individual life of the sample bank employees. It is thus, necessary to make stress free and peaceful work environment in the bank branches to deliver quality and safe customer services. The bank management can appoint sufficient number of staffs and making them relieved of performing nonprofessional tasks such as delivering and retrieving documents, stationary disbursement and ordering, coordinating, or performing ancillary services to reduce the workload, work procedures and working hour's related stress. Therefore, job satisfaction and morale of bank employees must be improved to reduce the complaints from the customers and reduce the job turnover. In order to achieve this, though, the equality in making work schedule such as work procedures, job rotation and providing leave can be implemented to achieve the above aims.

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